

**WATER
SPLITTING
GROUP**

ILLUSTRATIVE GUIDE FOR ELABFTW EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOLS

by the Water Splitting Group

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General remarks

Since 2022, the **Water Splitting Group** has been using **eLabFTW** as its primary — and only — platform for laboratory documentation. To ensure **consistency, clarity, and reproducibility** in our research, we strongly encourage all members to continuously develop and refine their use of this tool.

This **Illustrative Guide to eLabFTW Experimental Protocols** has been created to provide clear guidelines and explanations on how to write and complete protocols in accordance with the group's standards. It serves as a practical reference for filling out the group's **Default Template** (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16919055>), helping researchers document their work in a structured, transparent, and reproducible way.

The guide is a **living document**, regularly updated to reflect the evolving needs of our research and the collective input of our members. Beyond supporting our own group, we also wish to share this **Illustrative Guide** with other research teams beginning their journey with eLabFTW. We hope it will serve both as an **inspiration** and as a **practical example** of the many possibilities electronic laboratory documentation offers in advancing collaborative and reproducible science.

We gratefully acknowledge the contributions of all current and former members who have shaped this guide: **Kristína Rabatinová, Nadzeya Brezhneva, Alexander Eith, Ebrahim Abedini, Gustav Döhring, Muhammad Zeeshan, Michael Eshak, Ahmad Said, and Jacob Schneidewind.**

Their collective efforts have made this **Illustrative Guide** a resource not only for our group, but also for the wider scientific community.

Status of the Guide

This **Illustrative Guide** reflects the status of **August 2025** and is based on **eLabFTW version 4.x.x**. It provides the essential steps to begin writing experimental protocols in eLabFTW.

For more detailed instructions and technical documentation, please consult the official user manual: <https://doc.elabftw.net/>.

This **Illustrative Guide** focuses specifically on writing experimental protocols using the group's **Default Template**, which has been developed internally and is continuously refined according to the group's needs.

You can find the **Default Template** under: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16919055>.

Section: Experiments

Searching tools

Experiments are classified according to their **category** (*Filter category*). Categories are used for different research projects in our group. Furthermore, they can be classified in accordance with the current status (*Filter status:*), who performed the experiment (*Filter owner*), used tags (*Tags*) and many other functions.

Table 1: Overview of available **status** for experimental protocols.

<i>Running</i>	current experiment is in progress during the day/days
<i>Done</i>	the experiment has been finished and the description of the experiment as well as analytics has been performed
<i>Need to be redone</i>	the experiment has been finished, however the results are not satisfactory and we need to repeat the experiment so as to obtain reliable results
<i>Unsuccessful</i>	the attempt of the new experiment has failed
<i>Planned</i>	the experiment has not been started yet but is planned for the near future
<i>Info</i>	used for personal overviews, backups for master thesis or presentations, general informations...
<i>Documentation to be completed</i>	the experiment has already been performed, however the description of the experiment needs to be completed
<i>Analytics to be completed</i>	the experiment has already been performed, however the analytic data needs to be completed
<i>R.I.P.</i>	the attempt was unsuccessful and sad, and we will not come back to it
<i>TBD</i>	unclear status of experiment (to be determined)
<i>Further work ongoing</i>	used if the main part of the experiment is finished e.g. the synthesis and only a small amount is missing e.g. the preparation for the analytics

Starting an experiment protocol

Parameters and more can be specified for each experiment once starting a new experiment. For this click on the blue button **Create** and choose **Default Template**. The **Default Template** is specific to the work of the Water Splitting Group. From now on the following chapters will focus on detailed description how to fill in the template.

Always delete what you don't need from the default template (e.g.: Irradiation parameter or Future recommendations), and fill in your work to the available tables.

Experiment window

The screenshot shows the 'Experiments' interface. At the top, there are navigation options: '< Back to listing', 'Edit', and 'Duplicate'. A 'Create' button is in the top right. Below the navigation is a toolbar with icons for editing, duplicating, locking, calendar, and downloading. A row of tags is displayed: 'Radiation', 'C3N4', 'AE', 'H2O2', 'Red phosphorus', and 'NB'. Below the tags, the experiment name is 'NB-AE-002: Photocatalytic H2O2 formation, g-C3N4/ORP, white LED, (without O2 measurements), without degassing I'. The start date is '2024-02-08'. Underneath is a 'Reaction scheme/sample structure' section containing two chemical reactions: $2\text{H}_2\text{O} \xrightarrow{\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{ORP}} \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + 2\text{e}^- + 2\text{H}^+$ and $\text{O}_2 + 2\text{e}^- + 2\text{H}^+ \xrightarrow{\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{ORP}} \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$. Red arrows point from text labels to specific elements in the interface: 'Tags' points to the tag row, 'Name of the experiment' points to the experiment title, 'Start date of the experiment' points to the date, and 'PNG image exported from ChemDraw illustrating reactions that take place during the process' points to the reaction scheme.

The *Pencil* button allows editing existing protocol, the button showing two sheets allows duplicating the existing protocol with all details with or without the attachments. Duplicating of experiments will speed up your documentation in the future.

Tags

Tags related to the experiment are listed in the row. Never be afraid to use tags.

Tags that need to be always included: *Shortcut of the owner/participant*, *Type of procedure*, *Analytical procedure*. Other tags are decided by the owner depending on your own preferences. It should include more data on either the starting materials or the product.

Table 2: Summary of important tags which are mandatory for every group member.

Important tags	Meaning
<i>Shortcut of the owner</i>	Owner of experiment
<i>Experiment Category</i>	e.g.: "Radiation", "Titration", "Ligand synthesis", ...
<i>Analytical procedures</i>	e.g.: "UV/Vis", "ESI-MS", "MALDI", "NMR", "1H", "13C", ... (NMR tag is always coupled with the respective nucleus in separate tags)
<i>Others</i>	e.g.: starting material, product, ligand, what you want (these are used specific)
"Reference procedure"	If the synthetic protocol should be used as a reference for reproduction in the future
"Reference analytics"	If the analytical data should be used as a reference in the future
"Future"	If something went wrong during the synthesis OR if future recommendations are listed in the experiment
"Degassed"	used for degassing of solvent
"Python"	Tag to be used when a Python script was uploaded with the experiment for data analysis
"Commercial"	Reference analytical data of commercial compounds

Taking pictures during the preparative part

Important part, which takes already place during the performance of the experiment is taking pictures. During the preparative part of the work pictures should be taken for important observations, changes in the reaction mixture, new set-ups, and important steps in the reaction.

The pictures are then uploaded and linked to the respective steps in the Procedure/observation or the Product Characterization parts (see above). Every picture linked in the protocol needs to have a description (what is seen in the picture, *change of color, solid, etc.*) in the observations.

Writing of the Experimental Protocol

General remarks

Always delete what you don't need from the **Default template** (e.g.: Irradiation parameter or Future recommendations), there should be no empty tables.

Linking of protocols and other experiments: use "#" with this a search field is open and then you can type the experiment number or the title, click on it and it should be linked.

Adding of pictures/.docx/.jpeg/.nmrium and others: the file is added through the drop and drag and the bottom of the edit window. Once the respective file is uploaded, the name of the file can be copied and added to the text at the wanted position.

In every table except for procedure/observation parts "/" should be used if the field is not needed/used/given.

Experiment: Title

Title of the protocol includes the owners shortcut, if several people are involved in the experiment we include abbreviations of them all, separated with minus sign. Afterwards, the number of the experiment is listed (starting from 001) and the sign ":" is put for the separation from title itself.

Reaction Scheme

Reaction scheme/sample structure should include the PNG file created with the use of ChemDraw that contains illustration of the reaction that will be performed or the structure of the substance(s) under

consideration. The option Drag and drop is used for transferring the image to the field, the size of the imported image can be adjusted. In addition to PNG file, we also upload an original ChemDraw file (.cdxml). The chemdraw file is linked below the PNG file.

Literature/reference Experiments

Literature	insert the .doi-link if the procedure was reproduce/adapted/inspired from literature procedure(s)
Reproduction	for experiments which are reproduced 1:1 (same scale, reagents, procedure) either from previous experiments (then link the experiment), usually used for catalysis
Similar Experiments	for similar experiments where one or multiple of the parameters are changed, e.g. if scale up procedures are done

Reagents

Fill in the table. If the reagents are commercially available add the CAS-Nr. from the one which was used. Also, include the internal inventory number (when applicable). If the reagents are self-synthesised the experiment should be linked (this applies to the degassed/distilled solvent or any reagent as well).

Fill in the used amount, molar mass etc., provide all necessary informations (e.g. when a specific volume of a reagent is added give the volume, as well as the density and mass). For used solvents it is enough to just state the used volume. It needs to be specified if the solvent was dried or degassed.

“Specific” Parameters

Here we have either "*Irradiation Parameter*", "*Ultrasonication Parameter*", "*Microwave Parameters*", "*Column purification parameters*" or "*Furnace Parameters*". These are all device specific parameters which are stated in a tabular form. This should be filled if the procedures were performed, otherwise it should be deleted. This can be always added and deleted.

Procedure/Observation

Choose one of the *yellow sentences* at the beginning which works for your work, otherwise delete. Additional general remarks perform throughout the whole experiment should be stated in the beginning.

For the procedure/observation the column **Date**, **Time**, **Step** (here the performed procedure has to be written down), **Observations** (here important observation/behaviour/changes should be written down and the respective picture should be added) and **Picture** are listed. Explanations or important notes can be added to the procedure column (e.g. writing "**Note**:" or "**Explanation**:")

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Procedure/observations			
Date	Time	Step	Observations
All steps (unless stated otherwise) were carried out under argon using either standard Protocol - Schlenk Technique or in an argon filled glovebox (MBRAUN). ← use only when needed			
17.01.23		Two schlenk flasks (10 mL, 25 mL) were prepared.	
		The cooler was set on vacuum for 1.5 h.	
	13:30	The [Ru] was weighed at air and placed into the 10 mL schlenk flask. The atmosphere was changed to argon.	
	15:00	The ligand was weighed at air and placed into the 25 mL schlenk flask. The atmosphere was changed to argon.	
	15:40	To the ligand THF (1.2 mL) were added. To the [Ru] THF (1 mL) was added.	ligand : did not solved in THF ligand_thf.jpeg [Ru] did not solved completely, otherwise red solution
	15:50	The [Ru] suspension was added to the ligand solution under stirring.	add_ru.jpeg
		The flask was attached to the cooler in argon counter stream.	
	16:00	The heating to 71 °C was started.	
	16:20 (17.01.) - 09:00 (18.01.)	The reaction mixture was heated at 71 °C o.n. linked the respective protocol	17/01 → orange solution with yellow precipitation 1701_0900.jpeg
17.01.24	09:00 - 11:30	The stirring was stopped and the reaction mixture was cooled down to r.t.	after_cooling.jpeg
	11:30	The reaction mixture was filtrated according to the Protocol - Filtration with frit technique (pore nr. 4). The obtained solid was washed with THF (2 mL).	yellow solid → KRA-108-1 KRA-108-1.jpeg orange solution → KRA-108-2 KRA-108-2.jpeg
	11:50 - 13:30	The solid was dried in vacuum.	pale yellow solid
	11:50 (18.01.) - 13:45	KRA-108-2 was stored in the fume hood at r.t.	
		Small amount of the solid was placed each into two GC vials → IR and MS KRA-108-1-A: NMR of KRA-108-1 in DMSO-d ₆ using Protocol - Preparation of NMR Sample	preparation of samples for analytics in green color
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a schlenk flask (10 mL) was prepared the schlenk flask was attached to the filter frit 	KRA-108-1-A.jpeg

- Behind each solvent the amount for the step should be written down (e.g.: THF (1 mL) or THF (3 x 1 mL)) and this should be sum up in the reagents table.
- When a reaction step is done at a temperature other than room temperature, always specify the actual temperature (e.g. fridge/freezer temperature, cooling bath temperature, oil bath temperature etc.)
- The respective protocols and equipment entries should be linked.

Table 3: Color coding of text in the experimental protocol in section "Procedure/Observation".

black	General text
grey	Used for the preparation of set-ups (e.g.: "the irradiation set up was prepared according to ...")
green	Used for the preparation of the samples for analytical measurements, it is important to give analysis sample their own name
blue	Linked stuff (done automatically), hyperlinks can be added via link button on the top right of editor window
bold	Sample name for obtained materials (e.g. XY-001-1) - whenever a synthesis is finished and a material is obtained, it should receive a unique name, or when the reaction is split (separate name for each part). The sample name is placed into the observations column. Furthermore, each sample stated in the "Analytical table" needs to have a sample name in the "Procedure/observation" stated in bold (e.g. XY-001-2).
red	If you duplicate the protocol, color this red completely and then change the color to black once it was performed. With this it is known that this will happen in the future and is not performed yet.

Analysis

The analytical data is presented: **Date, Time, Sample name, Analysis method, Analytical device, Solvent, Raw Data, Processed Data, Comparative Data, Interpretation.**

- **Date and Time:** should be noted from when the analytical procedure was performed (in case of NMR it can be read out in NMRium file).

- **Analytical device:** In general it should be possible to identify, which device was used for the internal use. If there is an equipment entry it should be used
- **For the Raw/ Processed Data** the respective file or multiple file should be linked. If any processing did take place from the originally obtained file it must be added to the processed data, even if only minor changes were made.
- **Comparative data:** here a short description and the respective experiment should be linked. *Scenario for example:* additional spectra was added to the .NMRium-file for comparison with previous experiment, in this case the experiment from which the data was used should be linked in comparative data with a short explanation what it is (e.g.: starting material)
- **Interpretation:** short presentation of the results from the analytical data. If comparison with literature data is made, the .doi-link should be added here as well.

According to the performed analytical procedures the *tags* should be added: "NMR", "1H", "31P", "MALDI", "UV/Vis", ... "reference analytics", ...

Product characterization

The product characterization is presented: **Sample, Mass, Purity, Mass(pure), Amount, Yield, Description, Picture, Storage Location.**

- **Description:** here the product should be described and the respective picture of the product should be presented.
- **Image:** including image of sample (image should be named the same as sample (XY-123-1))
- **Storage:** here the place where the sample is being stored should be described (e.g.: freezer/fridge/fume hood, Schlenk flask, at air/inert). Once the material is used up or it is discarded, the storage location should say "empty" or "discarded".

Future recommendations

The future recommendations are presented: **Old procedure, Problem, Suggested new procedure.**

- **Old procedure:** the specific part in the synthetic procedure which went wrong/ did not work is shortly described or somehow highlighted.
- **Problem:** observed problem/possible explanation why it did not worked
- **Suggested new procedure:** future recommendation

If this table is used and filled the tag "Future" should be added.